

Title: Modeling the interaction between instabilities and functional degradation in shape memory alloys

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Description: The dataset associated with this publication contains the finite-element codes and the simulation results related to the modeling of the functional fatigue and localized phase transformation evolution in NiTi

Methodology: The finite-element codes were developed by using the AceGen system and the simulations are performed in AceFEM, both add-on packages of Mathematica. The postprocessing of the results has been done in the open-source platform Paraview.

File Formats: Finite-element codes are in .c format. The results are in two formats, the plot data in .csv format and the visualization data are in .vtk format.

Size: 15 GB

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Access Instructions: The full dataset is available upon request. Contact Mohsen Rezaee Hajidehi (mrezaee@ippt.pan.pl).

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